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DE-RISK PROJECT

DE-RISK aims at supporting the market uptake of renewable energy systems by fostering the adoption of LFMs and unlocking up to 100GW of flexibility in 2030 which will allow a safe and reliable integration of RES in the grid.

DE-RISK will achieve this objective by minimizing the investments and implementation risk through an innovative customer behavior change journey that will increase end users' trust and willingness to participate in the flexibility markets.

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon EUROPE Programme under grant agreement No. 101075515

DE-RISK

The adoption of Local Flexibility Markets to unlock the safe and reliable mass deployment of Renewable Energy Systems

MAIN ELEMENTS OF DE-RISK

01

Digital Twins Flexibility Platform:

High accuracy simulations de-risking the investments, implementation and operation

02

Customer Behaviour Journey:

Increase user engagement and active participation in the LFM

03

Multi-sided Business Models:

Ensure long-term and sustainable benefits across the LFMs value chain

04

LFM Regulatory Package:

Ensure fairness and competitiveness in the adoption and operation of the LFMs

05

Financing Schemes:

Democratize the access to sustainable investments

06

Exhaustive Validation:

Demonstrate DE-RISK holistic solution in 4 case studies located in Turkiye, Spain, Ireland and France

CASE STUDIES

Türkiye

Spain

Ireland

France